

Does ceramic tableware offer opportunities for emotional design?

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Abstract

This study responds to a perceived standardisation in design, which can be seen to result from mass-production, in a global market: It is concerned that product anonymity is contributing to a de-valuing of objects and thus a ‘throwaway’ culture. The paper argues that ceramic tableware can appeal to our emotional values and make suggestions for how an analysis of this can inform the design of emotionally durable ceramic objects. Coming from a background in Craft, the author’s research was conducted as live professional practice, aiming to contextualize and find relevant production methods for new industrial designs.

The paper begins by discussing the impact that globalisation is having on the ceramic market, and offers emotional design as a relevant discourse to counteract fast moving trends and production. A theoretical base is offered using Donald Norman (2005), and Jonathan Chapman’s (2005) theories of emotional design. These are then measured against the author’s ethnographic research, to demonstrate the emotive capabilities of the teacup or mug.

The paper goes on to explore existing examples of emotional design within an industrial context. It looks at how heritage, craft skills and user input can contribute to the design and production of ceramics, which are valued beyond their monetary cost. The author’s on-site factory visits, and interviews with production managers and designers, contribute to the argument that industrial ceramics can offer opportunities for emotional design.

Following this, new design concepts for emotionally durable ceramics, are offered: Three objects, designed and produced by the author, which are intended to be appreciated over time, are presented and the audience is invited to interact and feedback.

The paper concludes that, a consideration of the user’s emotional, tactile and social experiences with objects, could contribute to the design of ‘fewer better things’ (Maier-Aichen 2007). It

presents the notion that integrating individuality and uniqueness, into contemporary ceramic design, will encourage the user to choose and use objects, which they will value, long-term.

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Section One: Emotional Design and the teacup.

A discussion about globalisation in Design Week magazine warns, “The danger is that this information overdrive becomes a recipe for the ‘standardisation of ideas’ and says that “Plagiarism is a growing concern” (Fraser 2005: 18). This statement is reinforced with the comment,

“Inevitably our creative manifestations are starting to be the same.” (Rashid 2005: 18)

In the global market, production is accelerating and costs de-creasing; originals are undercut by cheaper imitations. The effect of this is seen in the mass of similar products shown at condensed consumer worlds like the home ware event, ‘Ambiente’ in Frankfurt: the high-end ceramic products on the top floor of the ‘dining’ hall are gradually imitated to a compromised quality and price as you travel down through the lesser known companies.

From the thousands of objects on offer, consumers are confronted with less opportunity for unique choices to be made as many objects begin to reflect one another in design. This speed of manufacture and commitment to changing trends (similar to that in the fashion industry) raises issues of both creative individuality and environmental sustainability. People are valuing the things they buy less, thus contributing to a throwaway society.

Emotionally Durable Design

In his book ‘Emotionally Durable Design’, Jonathan Chapman (2005) proposes that we might address issues of sustainability through exploring product life span and relating this to peoples’ emotional needs. He questions current ‘sustainable design’ stating that,

“...in their current guise sustainable design methodologies lack a philosophical depth, adopting a symptom focused approach...” (Chapman 2005: 9).

He goes on to describe a ‘utopian futurescape’ where design is derived from “...profound and sophisticated user experiences that penetrate the psyche over time.” (Chapman 2005: 18) for example, ‘refilling a fountain pen with ink’ or ‘re-honing the blade of a sushi knife on a well-worn whetstone” (Chapman 2005: 83)’. These simple, meditative experiences describe the repair and care which takes place over a long period of time, and demonstrate what Chapman describes as having ‘empathy’ with the products we choose to live with.

These ritualistic and meaningful experiences can easily be illustrated by both traditional and contemporary tea drinking rituals: Japanese ‘Way of Tea’ (Figure 1) and the British ‘formal afternoon tea’ use symbolic gestures and actions to show respect for, or to impress one another - thus imbuing meaning or narrative in the utensils used; as social signifiers, objects of communication and as performative¹ props, which must be learned, and practiced, over time.

Figure 1: The Japanese way of tea

The social importance of the tea-cup/utensil is also evidenced in less formal situations such as ‘taking a break’, ‘catching up’, comforting someone in shock or simply sitting down for a chat. Thus insinuating the teacup as an object closely linked with human emotion and therefore one, which deserves empathy.

Examples of empathy with ceramic products are illustrated by the author’s research into people’s preferred choices of teacup or mug. Questionnaires were used to collect descriptions of peoples’ favourite mugs and a cross section, from a range of age groups and backgrounds, was interviewed (it should be noted that few of the interviewees were working in design related fields). Intimate and emotional descriptions were collected due to peoples’, unquestioning willingness, to divulge details of their personal relationships with their drinking vessels (see Appendix A for results summary). The results of the interviews are evaluated, in the next

¹ During the ‘White Gold’ symposium at the Royal College of Art 2006, Emmanuel Cooper discusses the wide social implications of porcelain clay. He describes “..the performative aspects of porcelain...imagine a lady holding a tiny porcelain cup, her little finger extended.” (Cooper 2006)

paragraphs, against Norman's theories of cognitive and emotional processing. The results also reference the 'empathy' described by Jonathan Chapman.

Norman's levels of processing and the 'favourite cup' results

In his book, *Emotional Design*, Norman (2005) defines and describes the reasons we form attachments with objects. He describes three levels of emotional processing (Figure 2). The first, he describes as 'visceral'; it describes our innate and unconscious response to things. He states that, "Shape and form matter. The physical feel and texture of materials matter. Heft matters. Visceral design is all about immediate impact." (Norman 2005:69). Here he describes the judgements that are made subconsciously and quickly based on appearance.

Figure 2: Norman's (2005) Three levels of processing

In the 'favourite cup' interviews this 'visceral' interpretation frequently communicated: Comments like, "...it's beautiful and I like the contrast between the matt and shiny glaze" or "I like the simple design, uncluttered to the eye" were contrasted against passionate claims of dislike:

"Pig mug is my least favourite; big and clumsy looking. The brown colour around the rim is not inviting the design is garish and a bit ugly".

There were no real patterns in the responses regarding size, pattern and shape, thus suggesting very subjective reasons for forming these 'visceral' relationships. Here the majority of people questioned became thoughtful and animated, and surprisingly, when asked about their least favourite, some became noticeably agitated thus suggesting the strong importance of appearance.

The next level of processing which Norman describes is behavioural. This is to do with sensation or feeling. He states that, "What matters here are four components of good

behavioural design: function, understandability, usability and physical feel.” Interviewees also demonstrated this level of processing, by describing size, weight, the thickness (or thinness) of the ceramic body and again were noticeably disturbed when functionality was not up to scratch:

“...can’t really see what you’re drinking – huge amount of liquid – horrible to hold...”

Interestingly, some of these comments came from people who had initially denied caring what they drank from, suggesting less conscious but frequent emotional responses to the ceramic forms. These passionate judgements of good or bad design can be seen as indicators of the subjects’ emotional and intimate involvement with ceramic tableware; suggesting that their clear awareness of, and expectations about, design, can be used to inform designs for emotional engagement.

Norman’s reflective level of design is more complex and conscious:

“...it is about the meaning of things, the personal remembrances something evokes...it is about self image and the message a product sends to others.”(Norman 2005: 84)

He argues that, “ reflective design...is about long-term relations, about the feelings of satisfaction produced by owning, displaying and using a product” (Norman 2005: 38).

The most obvious emotional responses [in the favourite cup interviews] were presented here. John, a 31-year-old workshop technician, relates: “When I go round to my mum’s, she’s got a set with William Morris print. One is slightly distorted and has an oval rim, I always use it...I feel sorry for it.” The cup, here, is attributed sympathy as if it were human and John unashamedly demonstrates his empathy for the odd one out.

Reflective processing was also noted when interviewees talked about, the people who had given them the cups, and the symbolism of the objects. Here the objects represent events and relationships as well as being statements about the person who owns them: Gemma’s favourite is the ‘Kylie’ mug, a souvenir and admission of taste. Ron’s least favourite is the Charles and Di one [commemorative mug for Prince Charles and Lady Dianna’s wedding]: “...I think the Monarchy is a load of old ****!” (Ron Lacey 2007). These are the parts that, it seems, the designer cannot (or perhaps should not) try to contrive. However, the user autonomy, which is asserted here, is evidently connected to the social, cultural or emotional value of the object. And perhaps suggests that the designer might want to look at ways in which to leave space in the design for the consumers own interpretation.

Conclusions

Norman (2005) argues that three levels of human processing affect our emotional reactions to objects: the visceral, behavioural and the reflective. This suggests that both the sensory and symbolic elements of an object contribute to the value, which 'every day things' are attributed.

Chapman suggests designing for empathy as a potential, but perhaps utopian, antidote to the global drain on resources from mass production. His ideas give importance to the experiences we share with the objects we own and therefore suggest that the lifespan of the object should be considered as part of the design process.

The mug is emotionally valued, can be related to Norman's (2005) visceral and behavioural levels of processing. The shape, surface and weight can have an effect on the users' emotional response so this offers some useful, though not new, design solutions regarding ergonomics.

In terms of using Norman's model to inform emotional design, problems arise when the reflective level is considered. It is the user who applies meaning after manufacture, and it is questionable as to whether this element can, or indeed, should be designed.

An emotionally durable tea set, which would please everyone, would have to be a large, small, earthenware, china, thick, thin, chosen, acquired, gift set of cups and mugs; which need to be adapted or learned over time: obviously an impossible task. However, by isolating just some of the results, a focus on uniqueness could allow for personal choices to be made and therefore some user autonomy. Slight differences within a set, or unique and unusual functions, may be a feasible start in designing a range of tableware, which evokes an individual and long-lasting experience.

Section Two: Emotional Design in industry

Section two highlights cultural, and design, elements that may be exploited during the design and manufacture process within the context of industrial ceramic production.

Having experienced the 'Non-temporary ceramics' range (Figure. 3, below), designed by Hella Jongerius at the Design Museum in London 2006, and being impressed by the obvious hand-finished, tactile quality, which was achieved in a factory setting, the author began exploring how

her own designs could be translated from the ‘uniqueness’ of the hand-made, into the multiples of industrial production. Spending a week producing pieces and informally interviewing staff, at the Dudson Ltd Factory in Stoke on Trent provided first hand experience and an intimate insight into production in one of the few remaining British factories. Other personal encounters (as described below in sub-section ‘**Tac 1**’) contribute to the argument that attention to detail and a consideration of the product experience, can affect the users emotional response.

Dudson Ltd

As described in section one, the global market is having a huge impact on local industries: The well known UK manufacturers, Wedgwood, Royal Doulton and Portmerion, for example, have moved abroad to keep up with the speed and competitive prices, leaving only a few smaller companies still producing in the Stoke-on-Trent potteries – the traditional industrial centre for British ceramic production.

In spite of the shift, of UK ceramic production, to Asia and Eastern Europe, Dudson Ltd in Stoke on Trent still manages to produce all of its ware in the UK. It prides itself on being the only family-run pottery remaining in Stoke, having produced ceramics for over 200 years. Peter Lawton, the General Manager of the company, explained that their customers want the heritage that the company offers (Lawton 2007). Julian Orr (2007), one of the designers, confirms this. He explains that the American market especially likes the ‘Englishness’ of their company as a brand. It seems that here, the back-stamp ‘Made in England’ is still working in that it is adding to the narrative of the object, which is a useful emotional trigger.

Lisa Brown, the surface designer for Dudson Ltd recognises that to stay competitive, the customers’ input needs to be considered, thus allowing a more personal and meaningful narrative to be developed. She claims

“I’m doing a lot of bespoke surface pattern. Hotels or restaurants really like it if they feel they have designed the tableware themselves”(Brown 2007)

By incorporating the identity of the purchaser into the design and giving them some creative autonomy, the object can represent the client’s unique identity. This collaborative aspect of the design process allows the heritage of the manufacturer to be married with the identity of the client - again fitting nicely with the reflective level of cognitive processing, where meaning is assigned.

Hella Jongerius for Royal Tichelaar Makkum

Another approach, which can be evaluated in terms of emotional design, is seen at Royal Tichelaar Makkum; a company which prides itself on being the oldest company in the Netherlands, claiming “...It lives up to this long lineage but lets itself by no means tie down by the chains of history.” The ‘Non-temporary ceramics’ range (Figure. 3), designed by Hella Jongerius, makes explicit the narrative and heritage of the ceramic material and traditional industry. This tableware set demonstrates the age-old skill of the company’s decorators, whilst modernizing the designs so that people can feel they are buying into something new. The half dipped ware enhances the tactility of the pieces – giving them a material integrity, which the user can quite literally feel. These details allow for the physicality associated with Norman’s behavioral levels of processing to be appreciated, as well as offering opportunity for reflection on the meaning of the pieces as descriptors of heritage and local skill.

Figure 3: ‘non-temporary ceramics’ for Tichelaar Makkum Jongerius (2005)

Tac 1

One further example is demonstrated by the author’s own experience. On drinking from the ‘TAC01’² teacup for the first time, (Figure 5) the lightness of the fine bone china was noted. This surprising element led to an investigation of the foot rim (a ceramists’ habitual reflex – to read the back stamp or check quality); unusually the bottom of the cup was completely glazed, which led to an exploration of the fine top rim of the cup; this was unglazed (a necessary design for production purposes). The experience of surprise triggered a process of discovery, providing the learning required to gain empathy for the object and to create a meaningful memory. This experience inspired some of the work described in section 3.

² Designed by Walter Gropius, manufactured by Rosenthal, Germany.

Figure 4: 'TAC01' teacup and saucer

Conclusions

The examples shown use the heritage of the factory to maintain a unique company identity that appeals to the emotional or 'reflective' choices that the customers make. The material qualities of clay are exploited to provide a tactile experience for the consumer to explore - paying attention to detail and quality and transferring traditional craft skills and knowledge into a contemporary design context: all elements which can be seen to add to the narrative and therefore emotional value of the tableware.

Section Three: Emotional designs for the contemporary tea-drinker

Alongside, and in response to, the research described in sections one and two, the author spent a significant amount time designing, making and testing in the ceramics studio. Experiments with surprising weights and unusual forms and functions for teacups, informed a playful process, which tackled the concept of 'unique' dining rituals. Ultimately, the designs needed to function effectively in real commercial contexts and also needed to be viably produced in ceramics factories, so the unique design elements needed to be subtle enough not to interfere with function or realistic production processes.

In order to understand the difference between studio handcrafting and industrial production methods, the author spent 3 weeks producing in factories in the UK and Germany, proving that the shapes could withstand the high temperatures of both porcelain and bone china firings. Though the pieces shown were hand-cast, progressive machinery was observed in one of the

factories, which showed the speed and innovative technologies, which are now being used to produce complex ceramic forms.

The following descriptions show items of ceramic tableware that the author (2007) designed and exhibited in conclusion to the two-year research project.

‘Click’ (Figure 5) is a generously sized cup and saucer, which has been designed to allow for conscious engagement. A sloping recess in the saucer causes the cup to sit at an angle; it is secured in this position by the weight of the handle, which, when the cup is turned, can also make it sit upright. If positioned correctly, the cup rocks into an upright position when a drink is poured therefore making the object an experiential showpiece.

Figure 5: ‘Click’, Emma Lacey 2007

A designer, at the Rosenthal design studios in Germany³, described the rocking motion as ‘novelty’. This defeats the concept of emotional durability if the novelty wears off however, it can be argued that this novelty can be demonstrated over and over again in social situations, such as tea ceremonies. Qualified tea master, Alex Fraser, has compared the ‘mindful’ performance of ‘Click’ and the precise movements it requires to the Japanese way of tea stating, “The ‘novelty’ and surprise can create an impression over time, through repetition” (Fraser 2007). Another impression was communicated by Nuno Mendez, Head chef at Bacchus

³ The author visited the design director, Robert Suk, at Rosenthal GmbH, to test ideas and receive feedback on the feasibility of specific designs. He used the other designers present for ‘quick market research’ (Suk 2006).

Restaurant in London. He sees the saucer as an inventive canvas for food styling: He immediately re-invents the piece to suit his interests.

The 'Slide' cup and saucer (Figure 6) replaces the conventional shuffle (the movement between the foot of the cup and the center ring of the saucer), with a sliding motion. This fluid movement allows the user to interact with it either consciously, or in a more unconscious manner, as when tapping ones fingers on the table, or doodling with a pen and paper. As a comment on the way people often re-design the functions of objects they own, the generous cup and the saucer can also be used as bowls. The shape of the saucer means that a variety of, round bottomed, vessels can be nestled into it; providing a degree of user autonomy in that the form or function of the piece can be changed.

Figure 6: 'Slide', Emma Lacey 2007

The 'Duo' tea and espresso sets, (Figures 7 and 8) replace the typical circular shape of a cup with a subtle oval; its elliptical form changes the tactile nature and ergonomic of the object, nudging the user into consciously articulating a comfortable drinking position. The handle, which is attached in varying positions on each cup, further accentuates this function. The aim is that the user 'gets to know' their own cup; choosing a favorite handle position, from a seemingly standard set, and finds a preferred way of drinking from it. Not only does this add the opportunity for personal value to be assigned (as seen in the favourite mug interviews), it also connects the user with the manufacture process: A human intervention occurs when a skilled potter in the factory places the handle, on or off center. The initial exploration of the 'Duo' cups, which is provoked by the unusual shape, should ultimately encourage a more subtle fondness, which grows over time, ideally until the cup becomes protected as the favourite.

Figures 7 and 8: 'Duo', Emma Lacey 2007

The three designs make tangible concepts that can be applied to whole tableware ranges. What features in all sets is a subtle subversion of form or function and the fact that the user is encouraged to interact with, and experience, the object on a conscious level. This will hopefully instill emotional value onto the pieces as they are learned over time and become associated with personal and social interactions.

Conclusion

The 'favourite mug' interviews, described in the first section, prove our emotional attachments to ceramic objects and give tangible examples to illustrate Donald Norman and Jonathan Chapman's ideas about emotional design. The results suggest that a consideration of tactility and comfort, which takes user feedback into account, might contribute to the value attached to the object. It could be argued that this is simply a question of good design, however the wide breadth of personal preference suggests that it may be useful to consider a level of user autonomy. This is demonstrated in the author's design, 'Slide' where a set could be compiled of an eclectic range of pieces collected over time and used according to differing functional needs or preferences. The 'Duo' sets also provide opportunity for personal choice of a favourite therefore allowing the user to form a personal relationship.

The interviews also show more reflective interpretations of objects: those, which reveal details about a person's self-image or experience. Though it would be impossible for the designer to control the emotional attachments which the consumer creates, regardless of design and based on personal experience, values which can be viewed according to Norman's reflective level of processing, have been successfully exploited in the examples in section two. Here manufacturers have used tradition and skill, in a contemporary context, to appeal to their client's

emotional connections with the heritage of the company as well as their desire to buy contemporary products.

As with Hella Jongerius' range for Tichelaar Makkum, or the 'Duo' sets designed by the author, a human element can be factored into industrial production processes. This human touch can be seen in 'the author's 'Comfy Mugs' (Figure 9) where the form has been dented while still soft. Similarly this is evident in tableware designed by Bodo Sperlein (Figure 10). These examples, quite literally, connect the tactile experience of the user, and the fluid nature of the raw material, with that of the maker thus offering opportunity for emotional connection.

Figure 9: 'Comfy' Emma Lacey 2002

Figure 10: Salt and Pepper 'Pinch' bowls designed by Bodo Sperlein

Reflecting on the value attached to some antique pieces of ceramic; the collections people keep and show off, and the important function that everyday tableware performs in our lives, it is clear that ceramic tableware is a useful vehicle in the discussion of emotional design. However an evaluation of the emotional durability of contemporary ceramic objects will need to be tested over time.

Ultimately there will always be moral difficulties for designers in producing something that we might want to keep forever. 'Product obsolescence', as described by Chapman (2005) allows the designer to move with trends and innovate new things. However, especially, for the ceramics industry, due to the extremely durable nature of the material, it does seem that rather than mass-producing more objects, it may be better to design 'Fewer better things' (Maier-Aichen 2007), which show an awareness of the users emotional values and the products' life-span after purchase.

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